

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	High-frequency data logging with a list of the included sites
Deliverable number	D42 (Del. Rel. No. D8.3)
Revision	0
Status	Final
Planned delivery date	30/04/2022
Actual date of issue	26/04/2022
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	MPI-M
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

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1 Executive summary

This documentation shows that the high-frequency data logging has been implemented in the two NextGEMS models ICON and IFS and provides instructions on how to use this feature. The documentation also provides a list of sites for which the logging will be enabled, a result of the discussion between scientists and stakeholders. (Task 8.3)

2 Conclusion & Results

For specified locations on Earth, it is now possible to output variables, for instance temperature or radiation or wind, at a very high frequency, a frequency which can be as high as the model time step (in the order of seconds to a few minutes). As a comparison, over the full Earth, two-dimensional variables are only outputted every 30 min due to the high storage requirement. This high frequency data logging is needed for model evaluation activities and for the NextGEMS pilot project on solar power. Variables, location and sampling frequency can be chosen according to the user needs, as communicated to the modeling centers. After discussion with scientists and stakeholders, 30 locations were chosen for the high frequency data logging. These locations correspond to sites with high quality observations, with a renewable energy park or locations of previous field campaigns.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of NextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
Evaluate surface energy, water and momentum balance components as well as near-surface meteorology over land at storm-resolving resolution against observations and coarser resolution simulations (O1)	no
Represent land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolution by making use of the latest generation remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation (O1)	no
Prepare the NextGEMS models to best serve the science and applications, by implementing online output statistics co-developed with stakeholders, with a pilot project focusing on solar energy (O1 and O3)	yes
Expand scope of the SR-ESM by coupling it offline to a terrestrial biosphere model (O1)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

This deliverable is linked to task 8.3 of the NextGEMS project. As written in the proposal, in this task, scientists and stakeholders will select a few representative sites, for which model data will be archived (logged) at high frequency. Sites will be selected that have i) a high quality observational site, or ii) hosted a field campaign, or iii) are a location with a solar or wind energy park with high-quality observations. Those are needed for the model evaluation activities (task 8.1) and the proposed pilot project on solar power. The selection will happen at the first NextGEMS hackathon (i.e. the Cycle 1 Hackathon, see task 8.5). Requested technical developments to archive high-frequency output at these sites in ICON and IFS will be undertaken.

In the following, we describe the implementation of the high frequency data logging for the two NextGEMS models ICON and IFS as well as how to use this new feature. We then include the list of chosen sites for the high frequency data logging.

4.1 ICON

The infrastructure to write model output at selected locations on Earth (i.e. grid points) already existed in the numerical weather prediction (NWP) version of the ICON model (see section 7.3 in Prill et al. (2020)), but not in our NextGEMS version of the ICON model, which uses different physical parameterizations and variables than the NWP version. The infrastructure of

the high frequency data logging was kept but made compatible to be used with the NextGEMS ICON version. In particular, this required to update the existing high-frequency data logging to correctly handle variables employed by the NextGEMS ICON version, variables that remained uninitialized in the previous version of the high frequency data logging as not needed by the NWP version.

The high frequency data logging is controlled via a namelist. The namelist looks as follows:

```
&meteogram_output_nml
var_list = 'ta'                                ! List of variable names
lmeteogram_enabled = .TRUE.                    !.TRUE.=high-frequency data logging desired
n0_mtgrm = 0                                   ! Initial time step for output
ninc_mtgrm = 10                               ! Output time interval (in nbre of time
steps)
ldistributed = .FALSE.                        ! Do not separate file per processor
stationlist_tot = 52.17, 14.12, 'Lindenberg', ! List of stations
/
```

The parameters control desired variables, sampling frequency and locations to output. All can be freely chosen. The output is then written in a NetCDF file that can be read in by a standard visualization software.

As a proof of concept, Fig. 1 shows the high-frequency data logging obtained for the Lindenberg station for temperature.

4.2 ECMWF

The ability to record and output high frequency atmospheric and surface information at selected locations was implemented in the IFS model as well. To that end, an existing tool within IFS, DDH, was refined to output the desired information at the desired frequency. The scripts translating the raw IFS output to high frequency point-information were modified and re-written where needed. Moreover, to allow multi-year simulations, the output routine was changed to write one file per simulated day, and not write all the time steps into one file, which would have resulted in a too big file.

The high frequency data logging is again controlled by namelist parameters:

```
&NAMDDH
BDEDDH(1:6,1)=4.0,1.0,-59.4,13.2,-59.4,13.2,
BDEDDH(1:6,2)=4.0,1.0,-56.7529,13.613,-56.7529,13.613,
BDEDDH(1:6,3)=4.0,1.0,-57.121,14.1196,-57.121,14.1196,
BDEDDH(1:6,4)=4.0,1.0,-57.7165,14.3131,-57.7165,14.3131,
BDEDDH(1:6,5)=4.0,1.0,-58.312,14.1196,-58.312,14.1196,
BDEDDH(1:6,6)=4.0,1.0,-58.6801,13.613,-58.6801,13.613,
BDEDDH(1:6,7)=4.0,1.0,-58.6801,12.9869,-58.6801,12.9869,
BDEDDH(1:6,8)=4.0,1.0,-58.312,12.4803,-58.312,12.4803,
BDEDDH(1:6,9)=4.0,1.0,-57.7165,12.2868,-57.7165,12.2868,
LHDDOP=true,
LHDEFD=true,
/
```


Figure 1: High-frequency data logging in ICON with temperature outputted at the Lindenberg station for every model level and every ten time steps.

Figure 2: High-frequency data logging in IFS with surface variables latent heat flux, sensible heat flux and shortwave radiation outputted at the Barbados Cloud Observatory. Positive values mean flux from the atmosphere into the surface.

In this example, high frequency data logging is done for nine stations, specified by their longitude (e.g. -59.4° E) and latitude (e.g. 13.2° N). The numbers (4.0, 1.0) are settings needed to tell IFS that it is a point location. The latitude and longitude values are repeated because it is a point location; areas would have two different latitude and longitude values. The last two lines (LHDDOP and LHDEFD) have to be set to true to tell IFS that high frequency data logging is desired. Per default, the high frequency data logging in IFS outputs every time step and all variables.

There are currently two options for the users to obtain and analyze the high-frequency data logging. The output files directly generated by the model with all time steps and all variables can be used. Alternatively, once the model generates the output of interest, an easier-to-analyze output can be generated by running an IFS in-house executable (called `getddh` and `ddhrun`). This leads to the creation of ASCII files that contain the timeseries of only the variables of interest at each model level and at the desired sampling frequency.

As a proof of concept, Figure 2 shows an example of the high-frequency data logging of surface variables near the Barbados Cloud Observatory.

4.3 Station list

Scientists and stakeholders discussed the desired locations of the high-frequency data logging. These discussions happen at the Cycle 1 Hackathon and in follow-up meetings. Stations were chosen that host a high quality observational site (Lindenberg, Cabauw, Sodankyla Finland, ARMS OKL, Barrow Alaska, Summit Greenland, Dome C Antarctica, Payerne Switzerland, ATTO), hosted a field campaign (EUREC4A, MOSAIC) or are a location with a renewable energy park (IBER). Table 3 gives the locations of the chosen stations.

5 References (Bibliography)

Prill, F., D. Reinert, D. Rieger and G. Zängl, 2020, *ICON tutorial*, Deutscher Wetterdienst, available at https://www.dwd.de/EN/ourservices/nwv_icon_tutorial/pdf_volume/icon_tutorial2020_en.pdf, doi: 10.5676/DWD_pub/nwv/icon_tutorial2020.

Latitude [°]	Longitude [°]	Description
13.2	-59.4	EUREC4A 01
13.613	-56.7529	EUREC4A 02
14.1196	-57.121	EUREC4A 03
14.3131	-57.7165	EUREC4A 04
14.1196	-58.312	EUREC4A 05
13.613	-58.6801	EUREC4A 06
12.9869	-58.6801	EUREC4A 07
12.4803	-58.312	EUREC4A 08
12.2868	-57.7165	EUREC4A 09
12.4803	-57.121	EUREC4A 10
12.9869	-56.7529	EUREC4A 11
52.17	14.12	Lindenberg
51.97	4.93	Cabauw
67.37	26.63	Sodankyla Finland
36.61	262.51	ARMS OKL
71.17	203.52	Barrow Alaska
72.58	-38.48	Summit Greenland
-74.99	122.96	Dome C Antarctica
46.813	6.942	Payerne Switzerland
-2.145933	-59.005583	ATTO
-15.775435	-43.466896	IBER Minas Gerais/rad
-10.309269	-41.31803	IBER Bahia/wind
22.466893	-100.777205	IBER San Luis Potosi Mex/wind
22.087895	-101.602993	IBER Zacatecas Mex/rad
55.305482	-4.088157	IBER Scotland/wind
42.304491	-4.014777	IBER Burgos/wind
37.571131	-7.208683	IBER Huelva/rad
84.5914	14.7372	MOSAIC Polarstern in spring (warm spells)
88.8859	96.0429	MOSAIC Polarstern in autumn (rain event)
85.5852	13.248	MOSAIC Maximal ice production event in March

Table 3: List of high-frequency logging sites.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The now implemented high frequency data logging is part of the two model codes and thus is directly available to users of the models. The high frequency data logging will be switched on for the NextGEMS cycle 2 experiments, allowing users to look at the high frequency output at the selected stations. The NextGEMS cycle 2 hakathon, to be held in Vienna end of June, will also be employed to make users aware of this new feature.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This task contributes to O1 under A1 and to O3 under A4. The high-frequency logging build the basis for first interactions with users from the renewable energy sector. It builds a first bridge between the communities of climate modelling and renewable energy.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon, 19.10. - 22.10.2021 in Berlin
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 1.4. - 3.4.2022 near Madrid

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.